

MetaDocencia

¡2020 is over!

We came a long way.
We tell you about it here.

Our **Vision**

We are an inclusive and collaborative **community** that improves **education** by empowering instructors from underserved countries.

Our **Mission**

We are a non-profit organization that nurtures a community of Spanish-speaking educators by teaching **concrete, evidence-based, and student-centered educational methods**.

We collaboratively develop **open, reusable, and accessible resources** to foster **effective training practices**.

A lot has happened

1200+ teachers from **20** countries showed interest...

**Latin America
and beyond**

All our materials
are in Spanish.

The large presence of
Spanish speakers
throughout the world
make us reach countries
where Spanish is not the
main language.

... and we reached **all** provinces in Argentina

more than 700 educators

from Argentina and the rest of the world
already took the courses and are part of our community

<https://metadocencia.slack.com>
376 participants

<https://twitter.com/metadocencia>
1083 followers

<https://metadocencia.org/post>
25 articles

We met teachers from many disciplines

Useful contents for everyone

Those who took the introductory course by MetaDocencia teach these disciplines to **more than 19,000 students**

We met at many courses

- 34 Introduction to online teaching essentials
- 7 Introduction to online teaching 'à la carte'
- 8 short courses for INTA
- 1 pilot course on Zoom
- 1 course on learnR in LatinR

We took part in congresses, meetings and seminars

07/23/20

CarpentryCon

Laura Acion presents MetaDocencia as part of her talk

10/2-3/20

LatinR

Mariela Rajngewerc, Yanina Bellini Saibene and Paola Corrales deliver Introduction to online teaching essentials and the learnR workshop

10/22/20

Open Life Science

Internal presentation for the second cohort of students by Laura Acion

11/12/20

OpenEducationConference

Started by Laura Acion, followed by Nicolás Palopoli and finally delivered by Paola Corrales

11/12/20

Noviembre HD

A talk about communities of practices delivered by Yanina Bellini Saibene

11/17/20

PyConAR

Mariela Rajngewerc and Patricia Loto, assisted by Nicolás Palopoli, present the talk Good practices for teaching programming online

We received positive feedback

Romi 🌤️ 🏖️ 🌊 @romi_nahir · 21 dic.

Mi primer cuatri fue desorganizado y muy difícil de encargar, gracias a la ayuda de @metadocencia y la certificación docente de @thecarpentries aprendí un montón de metodologías nuevas y de formas de acercarme a los alumnos detrás de la pantalla...

CrstC @Crst_C · 28 dic.

Muy probable. En lo personal super recomiendo los cursos de @metadocencia para esto y para pedagogía moderna y basada en evidencia. A mí me partió la cucuza

Hallucigenia Divulgación @HallucigeniaOK · 12 dic.

Me cuelo para decir que @metadocencia fue alta herramienta y que de todas las materias virtuales en la que estuve como docente, la que mejor salió, fue en la que les tres docentes hicimos el Taller. No lo decimos nosotros. Miren las encuestas :)

Dr. Kari L. Jordan @DrKariLJordan · Sep 29

Attending the Open Source Community call I learned about @metadocencia and I cannot be more excited about this project!

Greg Wilson @gwwilson · Dec 18

"Building capacities to teach data science in Latin America" a wonderful initiative that is making a real difference

The Carpentries @thecarpentries · 14h

We ❤️ @metadocencia and are so grateful for the work you are doing to empower #RLadies in Latin America!

We received very, very positive feedback!

"The course was excellent. You gave me back the will to teach. I hated everything about having to teach online, but you showed me that you can do something nice. I couldn't even imagine the possibility of this being feasible. Teaching online can be much more humane than I could have ever imagined."

Emmanuel Iarussi, CABA
translated from original in Spanish

We have plans for 2021

Care, nurture and expand the community

Secure funding

New course: How to teach programming

New courses: How to teach R/Python

Scale registration process

Measure impact and publish

¡We are MetaDocencia!

- <https://metadocencia.org/en>
- <https://github.com/metadocencia>
- metadocencia@gmail.com
- <https://metadocencia.slack.com>
- <http://tiny.cc/youtubeMetaDocencia>
- <http://twitter.com/MetaDocencia>

“Shared joy is doubled;
shared pain is halved”

**Help us by spreading the word or joining the community.
¡We look forward to you!**

All our contents and materials are shared on the CC BY license

Main sources of our materials: <https://rstd.io/teach-online-2020-es> , <https://teachtogether.tech/> and <https://carpentries.org/>

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